

1 Title: **Decomposer food web in a deciduous forest shows high share of generalist**
2 **microorganisms and importance of microbial biomass recycling**

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4 Rubén López-Mondéjar*, Vendula Brabcová*, Martina Štursová, Anna Davidová, Jan Jansa,
5 Tomáš Cajthaml, Petr Baldrian

6

7 Institute of Microbiology of the CAS, Průmyslová 595, 252 50 Vestec, Czech Republic

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16 Correspondence to:

17 Petr Baldrian

18 Laboratory of Environmental Microbiology, Institute of Microbiology of the CAS, Vídeňská

19 1083, 14220 Praha 4, Czech Republic

20 Phone: +420 723 770 570, e-mail: baldrian@biomed.cas.cz

21

22 * these authors contributed equally to the work

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24

25 **Abstract**

26

27 Forest soils represent important terrestrial carbon (C) pools where C is primarily fixed in the
28 plant-derived biomass but it flows further through the biomass of fungi and bacteria before it
29 is lost from the ecosystem as CO₂ or immobilized in recalcitrant organic matter.

30 Microorganisms are the main drivers of C flow in forests and play critical roles in the C
31 balance through the decomposition of dead biomass of different origins. Here, we track the
32 path of C that enters forest soil by following respiration, microbial biomass production and C-
33 accumulation by individual microbial taxa in soil microcosms upon the addition of ¹³C-
34 labelled biomass of plant, fungal and bacterial origin. We demonstrate that both fungi and
35 bacteria are involved in the assimilation and mineralization of C from the major complex
36 sources existing in soil. Decomposer fungi are, however, better suited to utilize plant biomass
37 compounds, whereas the ability to utilize fungal and bacterial biomass is more frequent
38 among bacteria. Due to the ability of microorganisms to recycle microbial biomass, we
39 suggest that the decomposer food web in forest soil displays a network structure with loops
40 between and within individual pools. These results question the present paradigms describing
41 food webs as hierarchical structures with unidirectional flow of C and assumptions about the
42 dominance of fungi in the decomposition of complex organic matter.

43 **Introduction**

44

45 Forests are known to be vital ecosystems for maintaining the health of the planet, and
46 their importance in the carbon (C) cycle has thus attracted special interest over the past few
47 decades in the context of global change (Lladó *et al.*, 2017). In addition to the services
48 provided by these ecosystems, forests worldwide play the crucial role of C sinks in the
49 terrestrial biosphere, with C stocks estimated at more than 861 Pg C (Pan *et al.*, 2011).
50 Approximately 44% of this C stock is stored in soil, where microorganisms are the main
51 players in the decomposition processes and in organic matter turnover (Baldrian 2017;
52 Schimel and Schaeffer 2012). Since soil microorganisms have the potential to influence the
53 feedback between climate and the global C cycle, a better understanding of their role in C
54 fluxes in forest soils is essential if we want to model global C fluxes or predict them in the
55 long term (de Vries *et al.*, 2013; Rousk and Frey 2015).

56 In forest ecosystems, C is acquired by the activity of primary producers, trees and
57 other plants that fix atmospheric CO₂ and supply C to the soil as plant root exudates, transfer
58 C to symbionts such as mycorrhizal fungi, and produce dead biomass such as litter and
59 deadwood. Due to the fact that rhizodeposited organic compounds can be readily assimilated
60 by root symbionts and soil microorganisms, the decomposition of recalcitrant dead plant
61 biomass has been highlighted as the primary process that results in C sequestration (Xia *et al.*,
62 2015). Fungi are usually considered the principal decomposers of dead plant biomass, mainly
63 due to their filamentous nature, which allows them to colonize new substrates rapidly and to
64 translocate nutrients such as nitrogen (N) into this nutrient-poor pool (Voříšková *et al.*, 2014).
65 Furthermore, many fungi produce rich batteries of extracellular enzymes that degrade
66 recalcitrant biopolymers (Eichlerová *et al.*, 2015; Sterkenburg *et al.*, 2015; van der Wal *et al.*,
67 2013). Although less explored than fungi, bacteria also contribute significantly to the

68 decomposition of dead plant biomass in forest soils (Lladó *et al.*, 2017; López-Mondéjar *et*
69 *al.*, 2016). Of genome-sequenced bacteria, 85% harbour genes that potentially attack starch or
70 oligosaccharides, approximately 50% possess enzymes that degrade cellulose or xylan and
71 13% may target both (Berlemont and Martiny 2015). However, it is unclear how this genomic
72 potential is expressed and only few papers have touched on the question of the balance
73 between bacteria and fungi as decomposers (Štursová *et al.*, 2012). The combination of stable
74 isotope probing (SIP) and phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) analysis indicates that both bacteria
75 and fungi receive, on a short time scale, C from decomposing plant litter (Esperschütz *et al.*,
76 2011) and cellulose (Štursová *et al.*, 2012). Compared to plant biomass-derived C, the further
77 fate of C that enters the soil decomposition food web is far less understood since the fate of C
78 in the biomass of fungal and bacterial decomposers has never been addressed in detail. This
79 question is important considering that forest soils are rich in ectomycorrhizal (ECM) and
80 saprotrophic fungi, and their biomass thus represents a large pool of organic matter with a
81 potentially rapid turnover (Brabcová *et al.*, 2016; Ekblad *et al.*, 2013). The amount of
82 bacterial biomass in forest soils is considered similar to that of fungi (Baldrian *et al.*, 2012),
83 and the turnover rates of bacterial cell components have been proposed to be even more rapid
84 than of fungal biomass (Gunina *et al.*, 2017). The size, potential transformation rates and
85 relative enrichment in phosphorus (P) and N may be the reason decomposing microbial
86 biomass should be considered a hotspot of soil activity (Brabcová *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*,
87 2015).

88 The classical concept of soil C flow assumes that fungi and bacteria occupy different
89 functional niches: fungi have been proposed to be the major decomposers of recalcitrant
90 organic matter with a K-selected strategy, while bacteria have been expected to be r-
91 strategists mostly using simple compounds (de Boer *et al.*, 2005; Rousk and Frey 2015).
92 However, this concept has now been challenged by observations of the existence of r- and K-

93 strategies in bacteria (Fierer *et al.*, 2007; Lladó *et al.*, 2015) and the enormous phylogenetic
94 and physiological diversity within each bacterial phylum (Morrissey *et al.*, 2016; Trivedi *et*
95 *al.*, 2013), as well as by the predicted and observed potential of bacteria to decompose
96 recalcitrant organic compounds (Berlemont and Martiny 2015; López-Mondéjar *et al.*, 2016).
97 Recent studies have also shown that fungi and bacteria may overlap in substrate utilization,
98 suggesting that C fluxes in soil food webs are more complex than suggested by the classical
99 model of different substrate-defined energy channels (Kramer *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand,
100 the level of specialization for the different compounds constituting soil organic matter of the
101 individual decomposers within the microbial communities is also unclear. The limited
102 information that is currently available indicates that microbial ecosystems are dominated by
103 specialist taxa that overperform generalists in the degradation of compounds of a specific
104 chemical composition (Mariadassou *et al.*, 2015).

105 The aim of this study was to track the flow of C of different origins in the microbial
106 decomposer food web in a temperate forest soil. To do this, we have followed the respiration,
107 biomass production and C accumulation of individual microbial taxa in soil microcosms with
108 the addition of ¹³C-labelled biomass of plant, fungal and bacterial origin. We hypothesized
109 that although both decomposer fungi and bacteria are able to utilize compounds of different
110 origin, fungi are more efficient decomposers of dead biomass. In line with the observations
111 that litter of different quality supports specific microorganisms (Urbanová *et al.*, 2015) and
112 that microorganisms decomposing fungal mycelia represent a specific part of total community
113 (Brabcová *et al.*, 2016), we hypothesized that specialist decomposers preferring different
114 biomass of different origin, prevail. Importantly, this study should also answer questions
115 concerning the fate of the microbial biomass C in forest soils.

116

117 **Materials and Methods**

118

119 *Soil collection and microcosm set-up*

120

121 Soil was collected from a sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) forest in the Xaverovský Háj
122 Natural Reserve in the Czech Republic (50°5'38"N, 14°36'48"E). The soil was an acidic
123 cambisol with developed litter, organic and mineral horizons. The organic soil horizon was
124 1.5–2.5 cm thick, with a pH of 3.7 and contained 21.5% C and 0.56% N (Šnajdr *et al.*, 2008).
125 The site has previously been studied with respect to the activity of decomposition-related
126 extracellular enzymes (Baldrian *et al.*, 2010; Baldrian *et al.*, 2013; Šnajdr *et al.*, 2008) and the
127 composition and seasonal changes of the bacterial and fungal communities in soil (López-
128 Mondéjar *et al.*, 2015; Voříšková *et al.*, 2014).

129 Soil was collected from the organic horizon (pH 3.7; 21.5% C; 0.56% N), sieved using
130 a 2-mm sieve, kept at 4 °C and preincubated at 10 °C (the mean annual soil temperature) for
131 48 h before the microcosm setup to pre-adapt. Microcosms were prepared in 100-ml flasks
132 containing 5 g of soil and 0.08 g of one of the six ¹³C-labelled substrates, including ¹³C-
133 glucose (99 atom% ¹³C; Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, MA, USA), ¹³C-cellulose from *Zea*
134 *mays* (97 atom% ¹³C), ¹³C-hemicellulose from *Zea mays* (97 atom% ¹³C), ¹³C-plant biomass
135 from ground maize leaves (97 atom% ¹³C; all from Isolife, Wageningen, The Netherlands),
136 ¹³C-bacterial biomass of *Streptomyces* sp. PR6 and ¹³C-fungal biomass of *Phanerochaete*
137 *velutina* PV29, which were prepared by laboratory cultivation of the microorganisms until the
138 late stationary phase in media where ¹³C-glucose was the only C source. Parallel microcosms
139 with unlabelled substrates were also prepared for each substrate, as were controls without
140 substrate addition. Beakers with 5 ml of 1N NaOH solution were placed inside each flask to
141 capture CO₂. Microcosms were slightly moistened with water to reach 60% water content and
142 incubated at 10 °C in the dark. Three microcosms per treatment were destructively harvested

143 after 0, 7, 14 and 21 days. NaOH-containing beakers were directly processed. The microcosm
144 materials were frozen immediately at -80 °C, freeze-dried, and stored at -40 °C.

145

146 *Measurement of carbon isotopic composition of CO₂ and PLFA*

147

148 CO₂ absorbed in the NaOH was quantified by titration with 0.1 M HCl using
149 phenolphthalein (0.5%) as a pH indicator. The carbonates were then precipitated with 0.5 M
150 SrCl₂ aqueous solution, and the SrCO₃ pellets were washed three times with deionized water
151 to completely remove NaCl and other soluble impurities. After washing, SrCO₃ was dried at
152 60 °C and used for analyses of C isotopic composition. The ¹³C abundance in the CO₂
153 released from the SrCO₃ samples using phosphoric acid in helium atmosphere was analysed
154 using a GasBench II equipped with a cold trap and coupled with a Delta V Advantage isotope
155 mass ratio spectrometer (ThermoFischer Scientific, Waltham MA, USA).

156 The samples for phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) analysis were extracted by a mixture
157 of chloroform–methanol–phosphate buffer (1:2:0.8), according to Bligh and Dyer (1959), as
158 described previously by Šnajdr *et al.* (2008). The amount of 18:2 ω 6,9 fatty acid in the
159 samples was used as a proxy of fungal biomass (PLFAF), whereas the sum of the amounts of
160 fatty acids i14:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 7t, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 10Me-16:0, i17:0, a17:0, cy17:0,
161 17:0, 10Me-17:0, 10Me-18:0 and cy19:0 served as a proxy of bacterial biomass (PLFAB).
162 The content of all PLFA molecules (PLFAT) was used as a proxy of total microbial biomass
163 in all treatments except the addition of plant, fungal and bacterial biomass where PLFA were
164 also present in the added substrate. The fungal/bacterial biomass ratio (F/B) was calculated as
165 PLFAF/PLFAB. The ¹³C abundance in the individual PLFAs was analysed using a Trace
166 1310 gas chromatograph equipped with DB-5 column (60 m \times 0.25 mm), coupled to the mass
167 spectrometer (see above) via IsoLink.

168

169 *DNA extraction and ¹³C-DNA separation*

170

171 DNA extraction and SIP fractionation were carried out from triplicate independent
172 microcosms harvested at 7 and 21 days of incubation. DNA was extracted from 0.15-g
173 aliquots of freeze-dried microcosm samples with the FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP
174 Biomedicals, Solon, OH) and purified with the GeneClean Turbo Kit (MP Biomedicals,
175 Solon, OH). Labelled DNA was separated by isopycnic centrifugation in a caesium
176 trifluoroacetate solution (CsTFA) as previously described (Štursová *et al.*, 2012). Briefly,
177 three micrograms of DNA were added to the CsTFA solution with a buoyant density of 1.60 g
178 ml⁻¹ and spun for 48 h at 141 400 × g in 5.1 -ml tubes in L-100XP Optima Ultracentrifuge
179 (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA) equipped with the NVT100 rotor. After centrifugation,
180 gradients were fractionated into 250-μl fractions. Blank controls included in each
181 centrifugation batch with no DNA were used to determine the buoyant density of fractions.
182 DNA in fractions was precipitated with isopropanol at -20 °C overnight and centrifuged.
183 Pellets were washed twice with isopropanol, vacuum-dried and resuspended in EB elution
184 buffer (Qiagen, Valencia, CA).

185 qPCR was used to estimate the abundance of ¹³C- and ¹²C-DNA in fractions with
186 bacterial and fungal universal primers as previously described (Štursová *et al.*, 2012). The
187 labelled and unlabelled fractions were determined by comparing the normalized DNA
188 concentration in fractions against fractions of unlabelled controls and avoiding the
189 overlapping fractions; fractions representing the ¹³C-DNA and the ¹²C-DNA were separately
190 pooled for each microcosm. The data about determination, selection and pooling of the ¹³C-
191 and ¹²C-fractions from the different samples are presented in the Supplementary File S1.

192

193 *Microbial community analysis and statistics*

194

195 For microbial community analysis, PCR amplification of the fungal ITS2 region was
196 performed using barcoded primers gITS7 and ITS4 (Ihrmark *et al.*, 2012) and of the bacterial
197 16S rRNA gene using barcoded primers 515F and 806R (Caporaso *et al.*, 2012) in three PCR
198 reactions per sample, each as described previously (Žifčáková *et al.*, 2016). PCR amplicons
199 were purified, pooled by samples and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq.

200 The amplicon sequencing data were processed using the pipeline SEED 1.2.1
201 (Větrovský and Baldrian 2013) as described in (Žifčáková *et al.*, 2016). Briefly, pair-end
202 reads were merged and whole amplicons of bacterial 16S rRNA gene or the ITS2 regions of
203 fungal amplicons were cleaned from chimeras and clustered into operational taxonomic units
204 (OTU) at a 97% similarity level. Consensus sequences were constructed for each OTU, and
205 the closest hits at a genus or species level were identified using BLASTn against the RDP
206 (Cole *et al.*, 2014) for bacteria or UNITE (Koljalg *et al.*, 2013) for fungi. Nonbacterial and
207 nonfungal sequences were discarded. Sequence data were deposited in the MG RAST public
208 database (Meyer *et al.*, 2008), data set number mgs261719 for bacteria and mgs621722 for
209 fungi. The Shannon–Wiener index, species richness and evenness were calculated for 1,250
210 randomly chosen sequences per sample.

211 Two mandatory requirements were delimited for defining an OTU as ^{13}C -
212 accumulating (i.e., ^{13}C -enriched): 1) the OTU showed higher abundance in ^{13}C -DNA than in
213 ^{12}C -DNA in all ^{13}C -microcosms containing the same substrate; and 2) the OTU also showed
214 higher ^{13}C -DNA/ ^{12}C -DNA abundance ratio in all ^{13}C -microcosms than in ^{12}C -control
215 microcosms containing the same substrate. The OTUs not fulfilling both conditions were
216 considered as unlabelled.

217 PAST 3.03 (<http://folk.uio.no/ohammer/past/>) was used for statistical analysis. The
218 Bray–Curtis dissimilarity was used as a metric of similarity between samples. Differences in
219 CO₂ production and PLFA content were tested using ANOVA. Nonmetric multidimensional
220 scaling (NMDS) on Bray–Curtis distances was used to visualize the differences in microbial
221 community composition, and PERMANOVA on Bray–Curtis distances was used to assess the
222 significance of observed differences. Differences at $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically
223 significant.

224

225 **Results**

226

227 *Response of microbial community to substrate addition*

228

229 Microbial activity in substrate-supplemented microcosms increased significantly
230 compared to that in unsupplemented control as reflected by higher CO₂ production. CO₂
231 production was highest after glucose, hemicellulose and fungal biomass additions (Fig. 1.A).
232 Those substrates that induced the highest respiration also exhibited the highest ¹³CO₂
233 production (Fig. 1.B) and the highest share of ¹³C in the respired CO₂ (Fig. 1.C).

234 Total PLFA content increased in all treatments including the control. However, the
235 only significantly higher increase of total PLFA was after the addition of hemicellulose (Fig.
236 1.D). High incorporation of ¹³C into microbial biomass was detected in glucose and
237 hemicellulose treatments and was slightly lower in cellulose treatment. Higher total PLFAT
238 increase than ¹³C-PLFAT increase relative to control, was recorded only after 14 days of
239 hemicellulose treatment (Fig. 1.E). Since the ¹³C-F/B ratio was higher in all treatments than in
240 the control, fungi had incorporated more ¹³C from glucose, cellulose and hemicellulose into
241 their biomass than did bacteria (Fig. 1.F).

242

243 *Microbial communities accumulating plant and microbial C*

244

245 The microbial communities utilizing C from different sources were significantly
246 different ($P < 0.0001$ for both bacteria and fungi) and differed between 7 and 21 days ($P <$
247 0.0001 for bacteria, $P = 0.019$ for fungi; Fig. 2.A). In fungi, communities accumulating ^{13}C
248 from different sources showed a gradient along the X axis, from cellulose to bacterial
249 biomass. Moreover, fungal communities changed in time, with the exception of those on
250 hemicellulose and glucose. (Fig. 2.A; Supplementary Fig. S1). Although *Ascomycota* was the
251 most abundant phylum utilizing plant biomass and its components, *Mortierellomycotina*
252 dominated in the utilization of fungal and especially bacterial biomass. Bacterial communities
253 utilizing different substrates were more similar than those of fungi based on mean Bray-Curtis
254 similarities, especially those utilizing glucose, hemicellulose and fungal biomass. The
255 bacterial community associated with the decomposition of bacterial biomass was more
256 specific. Bacterial communities degrading cellulose and plant biomass changed profoundly
257 over time (Fig. 2.A; Supplementary Fig. S2). Bacterial communities utilizing bacterial
258 biomass were largely composed of *Gammaproteobacteria* (40%) and *Betaproteobacteria*
259 (40%), while other substrates were richer in *Bacteroidetes* and *Actinobacteria*. Not
260 surprisingly, the share of the slow-growing phyla *Verrucomicrobia* and *Acidobacteria*
261 increased over time (Supplementary Fig. S2). Species richness and evenness of microbial
262 communities were generally smaller in the ^{13}C -communities than in the control, but these
263 tended to increase over time (Supplementary Fig. S3.).

264

265 *Microbial decomposers and the use of C-containing resources by microorganisms*

266

267 In total, 134 bacterial and 81 fungal OTUs fulfilled the requirements to be considered
268 ^{13}C -enriched (Supplementary Table S1, S2). Among them, approximately 14% of bacteria and
269 12% of fungi accumulated ^{13}C only from glucose. Of those microorganisms accumulating C
270 from complex biomass substrates, most fungi accumulated C from plant biomass (75%),
271 fewer utilized fungal biomass (63%), and only 36% utilized bacterial biomass. Bacteria
272 accumulated C mainly from fungal biomass (75%), fewer from plant biomass (55%) and the
273 least from bacterial biomass (33%; Fig. 2.B). Twenty-three per cent of fungal and 18% of
274 bacterial OTUs accumulated C from all three complex biomass substrates (Fig. 2.B). Of
275 microbes that were able to utilize the components of plant biomass, 28% of fungi (and 28% of
276 bacteria) accumulated C only from the complex plant biomass, while 48% of fungi (and 53%
277 of bacteria) and 50% of fungi (and 51% of bacteria) utilized pure cellulose or hemicellulose,
278 respectively.

279 OTUs that were enriched with ^{13}C belonged to 63 bacterial and 30 fungal genera, the
280 majority of which were able to incorporate C of various origins (Fig. 3). Of the twenty most
281 abundant bacterial genera present in the soil, six did not show any enrichment of ^{13}C (three
282 Alphaproteobacteria, two Actinobacteria and one Acidobacteria); among eight fungi that were
283 not ^{13}C -enriched, four were ectomycorrhizal taxa (*Lactarius*, *Russula*, *Amanita* and
284 *Tylospora*). Of the enriched genera, bacteria exhibited a slightly higher proportion of those
285 that accumulated C from glucose alone (14% versus 10% of fungi). Additionally, the share of
286 bacterial genera utilizing microbial biomass was higher: 60% were able to accumulate C from
287 fungal biomass and 33% were able to accumulate C from bacterial biomass, compared to only
288 37% and 17%, respectively, of fungal genera. In contrast, a large majority of fungal genera
289 (87%) were able to utilize plant biomass or its components, whereas this share was only 65%
290 for bacteria (Fig. 3). Of those taxa that became enriched in the ^{13}C community compared to
291 the control soil, those showing the highest enrichment were typically common for multiple C

292 sources. This result was the case for the bacterial genera *Mucilaginibacter*, *Burkholderia*,
293 *Herminiimonas* and fungi of the genera *Mortierella*, *Pseudogymnoascus*, *Umbelopsis*,
294 *Cryptococcus*, *Astrotremella* and *Trichosporon*. However, in bacteria, certain taxa showed
295 high enrichment from only one C source, e.g., *Alkanindiges* on fungal biomass and
296 *Asticcacaulis* on plant biomass (Fig. 3).

297

298 **Discussion**

299

300 Our results show that multiple fungi and bacteria were able to use all C sources
301 occurring in forest soil independently of their origin and complexity. These results suggest an
302 overlap in the substrate utilization and the absence of different energy channels for fungal and
303 bacterial decomposers, as it has been traditionally assumed, and support the observations from
304 agricultural soils where both bacteria and fungi were identified as primary consumers of
305 simple, as well as recalcitrant, substrates; bacteria did not show a clear preference for labile
306 substrates (Kramer et al., 2016). In the same way, a field experiment controlling the C quality
307 in forest soils also revealed no evidence in favour of the classical assumptions regarding the
308 role of bacteria in the turnover of easily available substrates versus fungal decomposition of
309 complex organic material (Rousk and Frey 2015). It appears that there is no clear distinction
310 between the life strategies of fungi and bacteria in soils, and their roles in these ecosystems
311 are more similar than has been assumed thus far.

312 Despite the finding that both fungal and bacterial decomposers were able to degrade
313 complex substrates in forest soil, our results indicate that fungi accumulate more C from plant
314 biomass components, cellulose, hemicellulose and glucose compared to bacteria (Fig. 1F).
315 Importantly, our results indicate that the communities decomposing plant biomass were
316 different from those degrading their major components (cellulose and hemicellulose; Fig.

317 2.A), revealing the importance of other plant components (possibly less recalcitrant) as C or
318 nutrient sources (Fig. 2.B). Verastegui *et al.*, (2014) showed that the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ production from
319 labelled cellulose was substantially lower than that from simple components of plant biomass
320 such as arabinose, xylose and cellobiose. Here, we also confirmed the high recalcitrance of
321 cellulose to decomposition in comparison with the other substrates.

322 As a consequence of extracellular decomposition of biopolymers, smaller C
323 compounds are not only consumed by decomposers but also released to soil, where they are
324 available for the rest of the microbial community. The increase of labelled bacterial biomass
325 and diversity after 21 days of incubation may be the combined result of cross-feeding of
326 microbes on the biomass of decomposers, appearance of slow growing taxa and the
327 consumption of decomposition products by commensalists, sometimes termed “cheating”.
328 Bode *et al.*, (2013) showed that commensalism is of particular importance in bacteria. These
329 authors introduced ^{13}C -plant biomass in soil and used antibiotics, demonstrating that
330 inhibition of bacteria led to preferential ^{13}C accumulation by fungi, whereas the inhibition of
331 fungi (and thus decomposition) resulted in reduced bacterial labelling. The flow of labelled
332 isotopes from primary utilizers to secondary consumers is unavoidable in SIP experiments
333 (Chen and Murrell 2010), and it should be clearly noted that labelling is proof of C
334 accumulation, not of substrate decomposition. The bacterial taxa belonging to the phyla
335 *Acidobacteria*, *Actinobacteria* and *Verrucomicrobia* increased only after 21 days of
336 incubation, and the dominant members of the soil communities that were not labelled after 21
337 days also belonged to *Acidobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*, and *Alphaproteobacteria*, all of which
338 are slow growers (Lladó *et al.*, 2015). Since *Acidobacteria* and *Actinobacteria* have been
339 shown to degrade polysaccharides of plant and fungal origin in coniferous forests (Lladó *et*
340 *al.*, 2015; Větrovský *et al.*, 2014), slow or absent labelling may be caused by the slow growth
341 of these bacteria. If this explanation holds, it would indicate that the contribution of these

342 bacteria to the C flow through microbial food webs is low as a consequence of their slow
343 growth.

344 Our results also confirmed the importance of fungal biomass as a C source in the
345 forest soil and the important involvement of bacteria in its decomposition, as previously
346 reported by Brabcová *et al.*, (2016): the share of bacteria and fungi utilizing fungal biomass
347 was 39% and 15%, respectively (Fig. 2.B). In addition to the decomposers of fungal mycelia,
348 this group probably also contains cheaters. For example, some *Planctomyces* are known to
349 grow in association with chitinolytic microorganisms utilizing *N*-acetylglucosamine (Dedysz
350 2011). Notably, some fraction of fungal biomass has been found to be highly recalcitrant
351 (Clemmensen *et al.*, 2013) and is likely a major source of recalcitrant soil organic matter.

352 Bacterial biomass appears to be a very specific pool of C that is mineralized more
353 slowly than plant and fungal biomass (Fig. 1) and that supports specific communities of
354 fungal and bacterial decomposers (Fig. 2.A). Among fungi, the genus *Mortierella* accounted
355 for more than 80% of the ¹³C-enriched community. The ecology of these soil moulds remains
356 poorly understood (Uehling *et al.*, 2017), but the fact that they also utilize fungal biomass and
357 are inefficient decomposers of cellulose (Phillips *et al.*, 2014; Zeng *et al.*, 2013) may indicate
358 their importance in the recycling of microbial biomass. Bacterial communities degrading
359 bacterial biomass were dominated by the proteobacterial genera *Herminiimonas*, *Alkanindiges*
360 or *Acinetobacter* that are widespread in natural soils, and some of their members are known
361 to degrade various complex substances such as hydrocarbons and aromatic compounds
362 (Fuentes *et al.*, 2015; Kim *et al.*, 2014; Krizova *et al.*, 2014). Bacterial cell walls (such as the
363 Gram-positive strain used in our study as bacterial biomass) are rich in peptidoglycan, as well
364 as numerous and complex glycopolymers including teichoic, teichuronic and teichulosonic
365 acids, glycosyl-1-phosphates and other polysaccharides (Shashkov *et al.*, 2016), whose
366 degradation may be efficiently carried out by these specific genera. The role of

367 *Proteobacteria* in C sequestration and the mineralization of bacterial biomass was previously
368 reported by Lueders *et al.*, (2006), who showed the dominance of some Gammaproteobacteria
369 in the degradation of ¹³C-labelled *Escherichia coli* biomass in agricultural soils.

370 Fungal and bacterial decomposer communities were composed of both generalist and
371 specialist taxa (Fig. 2). In the case of fungi, the percentage of generalists was similar to the
372 number of specialists that utilized only one of the three biomass types (plant, fungal or
373 bacterial). The bacterial community exhibited a higher level of specialization, which appears
374 to be in line with our assumption. However, the relatively high share of generalist
375 decomposers, in addition to the fact that these generalists represented the most abundant
376 members of enriched communities, indicates that guilds of decomposers specialized for
377 different substrates are not so common as expected. The abundant generalist taxa of fungi
378 often belonged to moulds and basidiomycetous yeasts (Fig. 3). Basidiomycetous taxa were
379 reported to dominate over ascomycetous yeasts in forest soils and to be able to utilize a wide
380 spectrum of C sources, including cellulose, hemicellulose and phenolics, as well as products
381 of the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic plant materials (Mašínová *et al.*, 2017). In
382 forest ecosystems, the nutrient-rich nature of soil should support the existence of generalist
383 copiotrophs exhibiting high growth rates (Koch 2001); thus, slow-growing oligotrophs may
384 rather be specialists that often face limitations by their nutrient source. However, our results
385 show that generalist taxa are present among abundant and rare bacteria, rapidly growing
386 *Betaproteobacteria*, and slowly growing *Acidobacteria* (Fig. 3). For the latter, the ability to
387 enzymatically decompose various organic compounds was clearly proven (Lladó *et al.*, 2015;
388 Lladó and Baldrian 2017); therefore, it appears that there is no link between the growth rate
389 and the level of specialization. The absence of relationships between the growth rate, substrate
390 utilization profile and abundance in the soil was also recently reported for bacteria from
391 agricultural soil (Kurm *et al.*, 2017). Our results also indicate that it is impossible to make

392 generalizations about the trophic strategy for high-level taxonomic groups, since the same
393 phylogenetic group may contain both oligotrophs and copiotrophs (Morrissey *et al.*, 2016).
394 Further studies are therefore needed to address the ecology and physiology of individual taxa,
395 especially dominant ones (Lladó *et al.*, 2015; Pepe-Ranney *et al.*, 2016).

396 In contrast to the classical assumption about the dominance of fungi in decomposition
397 of complex organic matter, we demonstrated that both fungi and bacteria are involved in the
398 assimilation and mineralization of C from the major complex sources existing in soil. Our
399 results indicate that decomposer fungi are more suited to the use of plant biomass compounds,
400 while more bacteria possess the ability to decompose fungal and bacterial biomass. A reason
401 could be the contrasting demand of fungi and bacteria for nitrogen: bacteria that have a higher
402 N content in their biomass prefer to decompose more N-rich substrates, while low N plant
403 biomass may be more efficiently utilized by fungi (Fig. 4). This explanation is in line with
404 observations indicating that fungal biomass added to soil represents a hotspot of bacterial but
405 not fungal abundance (Brabcová *et al.*, 2016) and that the abundance of bacteria on
406 decomposing plant litter begins to increase only after the initial colonization of this substrate
407 by fungi (Tláškal *et al.*, 2016). Our results also indicate that decomposer food webs are
408 networks with a high level of recycling of the microbial biomass pool, rather than hierarchical
409 structures that would exist if biomass is decomposed by specialist decomposer guilds (Fig. 4).
410 Deciphering the complex structure of the soil food web is essential for understanding the
411 functional relevance of microbial taxa involved in the decomposition and for incorporating
412 the microbial dynamics into C-cycle models (Rousk and Frey 2015). Furthermore, although
413 soil microbes are the main actors in C cycling, their abundance and activity are affected by
414 higher trophic levels of the soil food web (de Vries *et al.*, 2013). In this sense, invertebrate
415 feeding on mycelia of mycorrhizal and saprotrophic fungi has been demonstrated to influence
416 C flow in the soil food web (Crowther *et al.*, 2013; Johnson *et al.*, 2005) and adds to the

417 complexity of food web structures. The incorporation of protists and soil fauna into food web
418 models appears to be the next important step to understand both the C flow and, ultimately,
419 the mechanisms controlling the sequestration of C by forest soil and to predict forest soil
420 responses to future environmental conditions.

421

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423

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432

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434

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602 Figure legends

603

604 Figure 1. Respiration and microbial biomass following the addition of plant and microbial
605 biomass to forest soil. (A) Cumulative CO₂ respiration and (B) cumulative ¹³CO₂ respiration
606 in ¹³C-labelled microcosms; (C) the percentage of ¹³C-CO₂ in total CO₂; (D) total microbial
607 biomass (PLFAT); (E) total ¹³C-containing microbial biomass (¹³C-PLFAT); and (F) the
608 fungal-to-bacterial PLFA ratio in the ¹³C-PLFA. The data represent the means and standard
609 errors of three replicates. *P*-values in panels indicate the significance of differences among all
610 treatments, and different letters at day 21 indicate pairwise significant differences between
611 treatments.

612

613 Figure 2. (A) Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis of soil fungal and
614 bacterial communities accumulating carbon from different substrates; dots – day 7, triangles –
615 day 21. Hemi: hemicellulose. (B) The share of fungal and bacterial OTUs accumulating
616 carbon from various sources: The numbers represent the percentage of the total ¹³C-enriched
617 OTUs that accumulated ¹³C from only one, two or three substrates.

618

619 Figure 3. Bacterial and fungal genera accumulating carbon from various sources and a
620 comparison of their relative abundances in soil and in the different substrates. The top twenty
621 genera of fungi and bacteria and all other significantly enriched genera are included.

622

623 Figure 4. Conceptual model of carbon (C) utilization preferences by saprotrophic bacteria and
624 fungi. The arrows indicate C flow, and the width of the grey arrows indicates the fraction of
625 the decomposer community that is able to utilize each compound. The brown colour indicates
626 the nitrogen concentration in each pool.